

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Ayedh**FIRST NAME:** Mohammed**PROGRAM CODE:** DME**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is:%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows **11**)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6-14)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15-23)
3. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33-39)

WRITE TITLE GIVEN TO RP

1) INTRODUCTION

The assigned course material for period one (1) was ACA-401D COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1) which was revised in 2021 by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck & Dr. Kabiru Gulma. This study material consisted of eight chapters illustrating and introducing the international academic and professional paper writing basics and mainly focusing on teaching academic writing at Euclid University, providing the basics on essay writing, punctuation, American vs. British English, plagiarism, and rules of styles, etc.

In addition to the course pack, a YouTube tutorials were assigned for the study of this period, the study material tutorial one was the Basic ACA-401 Tutorial (Cleenewerck 2016), and the second tutorial was about the instructor's Sample Review Video (Gulma 2021). Dr. Gulma explained the steps of reviewing an RP (Response Paper) using the review command tab in the work document and, step by step, explained the editing of the whole response paper in terms of tracking, deletion, insertion, and accepting one by one or as a whole.

In this response paper for period one, I will address the first four chapters of the study material (ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack 2021) as follows:

- Chapter One: Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6-14)
- Chapter Two: Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15-23)
- Chapter Three: American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24-32)
- Chapter Four: Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33-39)

In chapter one, the assigned material consisted of 3 sections focusing on the general overview of the basics of essay writing, the steps for writing a good essay, and some rules of thumb for writing a paper. The essay writing discussed in the book (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7) was intended for academic purposes and clearly illustrated the steps to be followed before undertaking essay writing as shown in Figure 1 (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 8). Furthermore, some key consideration for researching the topic, organizing ideas, writing the essay, and references were addressed.

In chapter two, the assigned material introduced punctuation marks, including apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colons, semi-colons, commas, dashes, hyphens, etc., as well as punctuation mark usage. It also provided examples of how punctuation marks are used and distinguished the differences between correct and incorrect punctuation.

In chapter three, the course pack introduced US English & UK English and distinguished the differences between US & UK English. As articulated in the course book Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021, 25), American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II, parallel to the growth of U.S. political, economic, technological, and cultural influence worldwide. In this part of the book, 7 points of why American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English" (cf. British English) were addressed. In addition to that, many different styles/types of punctuation marks were addressed, those are:-

- Different but the same spelling;
- Same term, different, but similar spelling and pronunciation;
- Same words, but different or additional meanings;
- Grammar, syntax, punctuation, general usage;
- Differences in usage with SBE "large collective nouns;"
- Differences in Usage with SBE "pluralized adjectives;" and
- Other common usage differences.

Not only the above bullet points but further explanations were given to distinguish the differences between both American and UK English.

Chapter four introduced plagiarism and how to avoid it, how/when to cite and paraphrase, and how to insert footnotes using MS Word. This is very key information for students to be aware of the necessity of avoiding citing information from a source without mentioning and giving credit to the author of that certain source of information. In addition to that, the assigned material introduced the methods used for citing a reference.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The essay writing chapter gave me an overview of essential essay writing and a clear understanding of essay writing as part of academic or fieldwork. Writing is part of my professional work in monitoring and evaluation, where we gather information, process it, and produce reports; therefore, this part was also very crucial for me to have further academic knowledge relevant to my work.

Some of the steps presented on page seven of the book got my attention and will be my guiding consideration to use as a rule of thumb for organizing my writings, particularly throughout my Ph.D. I wish I could have the confidence and encouragement to avoid any procrastination and start writing at an early stage of my study; that would allow me to finalize the RP (Response Paper) early, as well as would give me enough time to research, think, make modifications, and produce final high-quality RP.

The second, which is about defining the question, guide me to keep always the topic I am writing about in mind; I can also say that this aspect is the guiding question of my writing and present it well in a consistent way. The third, which was about drafting an initial plan, inspired me to have a plan in hand regardless of its completeness at the early stages. It would also be alarming to know about the schedule of your assignment, as well as be an enhancement environment/space for my research/writing scope.

The assigned material addressed key ideas to implement while researching the research topic for the essay writing; this included some key questions to answer about what is already known about the topic, what is needed to read/understand in order to write the essay, as well as learning about the usefulness of the topic, and whether it can be used to supporting answering the research questions. These ideas are essential for the students and not only for learning about how to write the essay but are also key steps and guiding questions that encourage students to be productive.

Organizing the ideas was one of the most important topics addressed in this book; furthermore, the essay format presented in the book, structured a framework of three sections which are the introduction, body, and conclusion, and provided the critical contents of each section which was very crucial to have structured way of writing the essay itself (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 9-10). In addition to that, the book familiarizes the importance of avoiding plagiarism and points to it as “A serious Academic Offense” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11), which confirms to have a reference section at the end to show the sources of any citations. Finally, in this section, I have learned the steps of editing the essay handling the essay and have earned knowledge of some rules of thumb for writing a paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 13-14).

3) PUNCTUATIONS

In this part of the assigned book for period one, I have earned a good understanding of the different types of punctuation marks, particularly the examples under each of the

punctuation marks showed an easy way to distinguish and understand their use. This part of the book addressed and articulated its contents in a straightforward form, and it will serve me to use as a reference for any writing until one. I believe in the importance of understanding punctuation marks and how they can improve the readability and the style of my essays/papers.

For me, the citations/referencing and punctuation marks are always confusing when writing, and I believe that this is a very key takeaway for me to become able to differentiate and use each in its proper place; not only that, but this will also guarantee that readers/audience of my reports/papers both for professional, and academic purposes will give attention to what they are reading and will be able to link the ideas and understand the essence my writing easily. I am very satisfied with the information earned and belief that it will enhance my writing skills and enhance it well.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Chapter three introduced US English & UK English and distinguished the differences between US & UK English. This was very useful to me, particularly since I am a non-English speaker, and it has given me many insights in regard to the differences. The assigned material addressed general categories of difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE). This introduced me to several key differences with examples that clearly illustrated and were easy to understand.

Still, some personal efforts would be required from my side to be able to separate the differences by 100%, particularly for my writing.

In general, I have grasped the fundamental differences between American vs. British English, especially since the chapter addressed differences in terms of spelling, pronunciation, grammar, syntax, punctuation, etc., which was comprehensive and satisfactory to my need for such information at this level.

I am looking at the different ideas, information, and knowledge that I will learn throughout my study from all the other assignment materials and particularly from my course instructor, which I am confident will add a lot of value and quality to my research and evaluation-related writings.

5) PLAGIARISM

This part of the course pack addressed plagiarism which is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information, as the book defined on page 34. I see that this part deals with the ethical issues when writing in order to avoid taking credit for one's efforts, same as the example "Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author" given in the book. The assigned material addressed the reasons why sources of the information have to be mentioned. I consider it fair to give

credit to those who have put effort into searching for a topic and invested time and effort to produce and gather evidence in one place, which is beneficial not only for them but also for everyone looking a similar evidence of a specific topic, or even use it to backup and support their vision/message or research topic.

I have learned a lot about the solution for such ethical issues, as clearly stated in Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021, 34), stating, “the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using.” In this regard, the book addressed two things to be aware of in terms of citing, and they are:-

- There are in-text citations,
- B. List of works cited.

Those above-mentioned methods were clearly articulated with examples in terms of the quotations and paraphrases, as well as a few tips provided in regard to this, and many other key considerations of times when not to cite, footnote, and references were addressed. In this part, I have grasped the advantage of citing sources and have learned the different methods of citing and referencing with footnotes and endnotes.

6) CONCLUSION

In general, the assigned study book (ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack) was straightforward to understand. It was informative with much basic information that has helped me gain a good understanding of essay writing, has helped me to learn the use of punctuation marks, the difference between American vs. UK English, as well as plagiarism, citation, referencing, etc.

The knowledge I have earned from period one (1) will not only be helpful to me at this stage but also be a reference for me throughout my Ph.D. study.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. 2016. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo.

Gulma, Kabiru, dir. 2021. *Sample Response Paper Review Video*. YouTube.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.